

MODIFYING THE SECURITY OF CLASSICAL CAESAR CIPHER TECHNIQUE USING SOME RANDOMIZED APPROACH

¹MR.SAGAR RAJMANE

Dept of Comp Engg. A.G.Patil Institute of technology solapur
sagarrajmane9728@gmail.com

²PROF.AARTI VALSANG

Dept of Comp Engg. A.G.Patil Institute of technology solapur.
aarti.valsang@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Cryptography is about constructing and analyzing protocol that prevents third parties or the public from reading private messages. There are two techniques for converting data into no readable form: 1) Transposition technique 2) Substitution technique. Caesar cipher is an example of substitution method. Caesar cipher has various limitations. In this paper we have focused on the well known Caesar cipher techniques. Here in this paper our aim was to induce some strength to the Caesar cipher encryption technique. This proposed technique blended classical encryption with the some more techniques and This method is better in terms of providing more security for any given text message. In our experiments we took Caesar Ciphers as reference of Classical Techniques. To make it more secure we have used some techniques like we have divided the given plain text in five word group each. With the given key rearrange the group of letters without giving the space

KEYWORDS: plaintext, cipher text ,cryptography, Caesar cipher.